

A European study on the current situation of Makerspaces and FabLabs

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Abstract

The present study evaluates post-pandemic European makerspaces and FabLabs. The aim is to analyse the spaces and the main actors, to find out the conditions of operation and technological adaptation that currently exist. By being closer to the users, managers, and technicians, we know the proposals they make and recognise their needs. Their technological contributions enable the prototyping of ideas and ventures, or facilitate and improve access to technology for professionals, makers, and other users. This contribution offers an insight into the functioning of digital creation and fabrication spaces, based on existing models of Fablabs, makerspaces and hackerspaces in Europe. In this context, new opportunities for connection between maker activity, society, and business, generated by the sustained growth of these spaces and their potential development, can be justified. In addition, we know the business model, its values, strategies, the conditions of access and adaptation of these spaces, as well as their potential as a business. Identifying and assessing its portfolio of services, type of demand-project by professional or business profiles, competences in the sampled activities linked to the strengthening of soft skills and through technology, with Industry 4.0, will facilitate how to intervene with the different actors of the system.

Keywords

Maker Spaces, FabLabs, Social fabrication, Digital fabrication, Collaborative work.

1 Introduction

The extensive number of spaces disseminated all over the world makes it difficult to establish advanced patterns for their classification, although they do have a series of common characteristics. One of the studies that interests researchers is that of Helmut Schmidt University (Germany), which highlights the lack of a formalised operational structure in the spaces and the lack of unified (networked) communication platforms, among other limitations. This is identified as two of the main impediments to the full effectiveness of the Spaces initiative. It is also suggested that it is difficult to make a comparative quantification of the spaces, nevertheless this paper used indicators of FabLabs' success that should be considered (Osunyomi et al., 2016).

Table 1. Ecosystem study variables FabLab, according to Helmut Schmidt University. Source: Own elaboration., based on OSUNYOMI et al., 2016.

NUMBER	INDICATORS
1]	Contribution to innovations and R&D
2]	Contribution to human development (i.e., in the empowerment of people)
3]	Achievement of its goals and objectives
4]	User types
5]	Contributions to entrepreneurship and business development
6]	Accessibility for users
7]	Sustainability
8]	Collaboration within the FabLab network
9]	Frequency of use
10]	Availability of raw materials

Since these indicators, the authors highlight outstanding issues such as the development of a sustainable business model, which impedes the effectiveness of the FabLab initiative. They conclude that it is necessary to show the important potential of these regional networks, through: (1) the provision of assistance to new companies, (2) the creation of appropriate networks, (3) good communication for the exchange of ideas and information, (4) the national and international visibility of each facility, (5) building a more credible business model in terms of marketing and financing.

The situation should also be considered that, given the differences that occur between the various manufacturing labs, a flexible set of guidelines can be envisaged, depending on the specific needs of the local ecosystems and the capacity of the existing manufacturing labs in their environment. Some of this materialized in the case of the FabLabNet project, funded by the Interreg Central Europe programme, which considered by country different approaches around their business models (Fellin & Barcucci, 2017):

- With communities, promoting digital transformation within the local production ecosystem, both in industrial manufacturing and craftsmanship,
- With businesses, supporting incubation, acceleration, and business development,
- Connecting with education, which focuses on training and education formats.

Regarding open sharing, there is also a debate given the open culture-oriented nature of the spaces (Wolf et al., 2014). The vast majority exhibit attempts to share their open-source knowledge and work with open innovation processes. Nevertheless, the other two features that characterize open access, such as open software development, and having open content in open education and science, are not common. This informal peer-to-peer communication can be part of a conscious building of a community and can generate significant knowledge production.

In terms of published cases of experiences on spaces connected to the business world, we have known few of them, such as the recent Smart Lab model designed and implemented by the Institute of Industrial Management of the FH Joanneum University of Applied Sciences (Austria), for the transfer of knowledge of digital transformation processes for business. The methodology they use is mainly focused on the validation of prototypes (Tschandl et al., 2020). On the other hand, already consolidated spaces, such as FabLab Lisbon (municipally run), are confident that the future lies more in professionalized services such as, for example, supporting incubation and acceleration of companies (Gaeiras, 2017).

Overall, the issue of makerspaces is still not sufficiently addressed in the scientific literature (Savastano et al., 2016), and if there is any, it has focused more on educational and training aspects (40%) than on

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end-user (20%), technological (15%) or organizational (20%) areas. Even so, FabLab or makerspace initiatives are for most authors of great importance to ensure the innovative and sustainable development of communities, both in developed and developing countries, and have an economic importance to support entrepreneurial efforts. Both makerspaces and other digital fabrication initiatives are therefore good innovation avenues to facilitate appropriate value creation.

2 Methodology

Due to the prospective nature of the study, it was proposed to carry out, on the one hand, exploratory research, and on the other hand, descriptive research. To achieve the general objectives and aims set out in this research, qualitative and quantitative techniques were used together.

Forty-four in-depth surveys were conducted with 35 questions, (included in annex), which were translated into six EU languages: Greek, Italian, Danish, German, French and Spanish. This survey was structured and distributed in six areas: general description of the organization, values and strategies, partnerships and funding, internal composition, communication and tools, and technology.

For this purpose, an Internet survey platform was used, universal and multiplatform in nature so that it could be answered by phone, tablet, or computer. It was structured in each language to obtain information by country and in its global computation. The link was used in each of the languages to be able to send through WhatsApp or mail.

Two expert panels were also held. The first of Spanish spaces, as representatives of one of the EU countries, and the second, with non-Spanish European spaces. Each meeting did not exceed an hour and a half, with the three big questions that kept the conversation going: (1) about the current situation, (2) about the future, and (3) about the economic and social demand for the activities of the most significant. The sessions were recorded with the purpose of collecting as many aspects as possible that allow merely reaffirming the data obtained at a quantitative level, from the surveys, and collecting expressions that can reinforce aspects of the final study.

3 Results

3.1 Organization model

The configuration of the organizations on which these spaces depend is very diverse, although the majority are those that function as small and medium-sized companies, followed by those that depend on professional or business associations, and those that are managed or have staff that are part of them. of the universities. There is also a significant number that appear grouped as NGOs, or under the umbrella of non-profit associations or foundations.

Its presence in networks, especially international ones, is very significant, and these networks are mainly related to digital manufacturing, especially 3D printing systems, and those linked to the DIY culture.

Promoted or created especially in the last decade, the organizations are very young and recently created. Since most of them are companies, they are in the process of commercial activity, although there are a significant number still pending activation.

3.2 Values and strategies

The spaces opt for main values, such as technological empowerment (86.3%), since the objective is that the people who participate or go to these spaces have access to and learn from technology to develop ideas and projects. In line with this, other values are self-learning, with 68.1%, and dedication to open hardware-design, with 65%.

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Other values for complementary spaces are digital inclusion, which strengthens empowerment and the self-learning process, standing at 70.4%. Other important values would be urban innovation (almost 60%) and the circular economy (56.8%).

Table 2. Chart showing by country the sources of financial support. Source: Own elaboration.

These values are transmitted in different ways, but the one that stands out the most as a whole is the organization of workshops and courses, with 81.8% from all over Europe. It would follow that this transmission is carried out through collaborative management and the way (maker) in which work is done in the spaces themselves and promoting free technological support.

The face-to-face model for working in spaces is practically absolute, as a verifiable fact throughout Europe. Even so, the online experience is already very widespread, and the two are combined by 75%. Only 22.7% maintain the face-to-face experience and activities without having the online model (although we understand that this happened before the effect of the Pandemic).

The space model is with access restrictions (34.09%) compared to the one that does not have access dependencies (22.73%). Within the spaces in which these conditions can occur, 29.5% are public spaces with great availability of assistance.

45.4% of European spaces consider that they are fully adapted and prepared to serve their public. On the other hand, 43.1% consider that even providing service they are not fully prepared technologically and organizationally to fully serve users.

Their radius of action or influence is normally municipal (with 68.1%) or regional (61.3%). The significant percentage represented by its relationship with Europe (36.3%) and international action is verified, with more than 34% of the cases.

The activities that are carried out most in European spaces, according to the user, are professional or business projects on the construction of prototypes (a ratio of 2.98), followed by initiatives or personal projects that are in 2.70 of the activities that are registered.

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Figure 1. Visit of Nadya Peek - MIT Media Lab, to check out the projects being carried out at FabLab Valencia. Photo: Ricardo Moreno. 2016.

Designers are the professionals who most frequent these spaces (68.1%), followed by 'inventors' (with 63.6% of enterprising and ingenious people who do not have a specific qualification or defined degree), and students (61.3%).

Regarding the type of projects carried out in European FabLabs and makerspaces, the most common are related to product or object design (70.4%), followed by electronics (59%), and the training of both children and young people, as well as adults (both with 56.8% respectively).

3.3 Partnerships and funding

The European spaces work for different types of organizations, among which 84.09% of public institutions (non-educational) stand out, and with 75%, indistinctly, companies and individuals. Therefore, we are facing a business model that works extensively and in a customary way with companies, in the same way that it works with the individual user, whether as a professional, student or hobbyist, and that has an effective and habitual relationship with the different institutions. local, regional, national, or European.

When portraying the model of the European space, it seems relevant to us that half of the sampled spaces do not receive any type of support, and above all have their own resources. Yes, being in networks, being subcontracted or participating as partners who receive or have received support from public institutions is recognized in 54.4% of European spaces.

Therefore, the four legs on which the business of these spaces is usually based (and this is demonstrated by at least 43.1% of the sample), are: carrying out projects with public funds, invoicing for prototyping services, developing services R&D for companies and start different training activities.

Finally, the results regarding investments are conclusive, practically all the spaces dedicate their profits to the maintenance of the space and technology, with 93.1%, and to the acquisition of machinery or technology (86.3%).

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Figure 2. Fundación Orange, digital fabrication training project. Breakers Collective, young people aged between 16 and 25 in vulnerable situations or who live in complex situations and have few opportunities to access this type of technology. Photo: Ricardo Moreno. 2019.

3.4 Internal Composition

We can affirm that most of the spaces (54.5%) place their teams between one and ten people, as if they were micro-SMEs, and with 31.8% of the total, organizations with less than 50 workers (what we would consider in Europe as SME). Small structures characterized as micro or small companies due to their size. Of these teams, the staff or the number of people who make decisions are usually two or three (the sample indicates that in 68.1% of the cases decisions are made between one or five people). On the other hand, the gender gap is evident in all European spaces, and the presence of women in these organizations is only 28.4% on average.

These teams are made up of a staff with 61.5% of graduates with university studies, they are of adulthood (52.4%), and the most developed soft skills are creativity (with 88.6%) and hard work. in a team (72.7%). They are teams trained in matters related to innovation (with 75%), where its members (according to 43.1%) carry out an initiation training, or an informal accompanying training (in 40.9% of the spaces).

3.5 Communication

We have seen is that perhaps one of the greatest weaknesses recorded in this study, since many spaces do not have people dedicated to communication (47%) and if they do, most are not specialized (25%). Even so, they have resources to communicate, especially through digital tools (of which 65.9%) have access.

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Figure 3. Left, Opening poster of FabLab Valencia Océano Naranja (2017). Right, Cover of Experimenta Magazine, a special issue dedicated to FabLab culture. Photo: Ricardo Moreno. 2023.

The European spaces usually update their information and document their work monthly (29.5%) or weekly (20.4%), and the same thing happens in this order of time when they update the web. (22.7% and 20.4% respectively). Its appearance in the media is verified through interviews (79.5%), or daily or current news, both in the written and digital press (63.6%).

To conclude this section, say that the usual communication resources with its users are social networks (90.9%) and email (88.6%).

3.6 Tech context

The most used software is 2D and 3D design (84.5%), which allows subsequent work to gain access to digital machines. Thanks to the manufacturing software (72.2), which prepares these files plus the machine programs, we can develop the elements and prototypes we want. This need for access is fully consolidated in all European areas.

Table 3. Chart showing by country the software used in their spaces. Source: Own elaboration.

Third, and no less important, is the software that allows electromechanical and computer applications to be programmed or developed, and which is often decisive if there is a clear orientation or specialization in these areas in space. Its presence is very common in 57.6% of the spaces.

Finally, the most common programs, which are considered open or commercial, such as those for data processing, administration, or for making presentations, are below the average, while data is still significant (with 45.3% for use in makerspaces).

Regarding hardware or technical equipment, three-dimensional printing systems are the most present technologies at 85%, giving a significant figure of more than 68.3% who have more than two 3D printers.

The next technology used in the spaces is laser cutting engraving, with a presence of 76% of the total. They are followed by CNC milling machines, either medium or large, with 67.2%, or small ones, with 64.7%. Nearby we have 3D scanning systems, with an implementation of 63.5% throughout Europe.

The devices that appear the most in European makerspaces or FabLabs are electronic equipment, which makes a total of 60.4%, and vinyl cutters or plotters, which are present in 55.9% of the spaces.

Far below these systems, we find the CNC metal cutting devices, which remain in 19.4% of the cases. We have already begun to talk about systems that may be more expensive, with greater space preparation measures, or because metal is not the priority material to carry out these actions. This digital metal cutting or machining systems are now joined by the lowest value of all, which is metrology devices, with 18.5%, perhaps for reasons of cost or functions that can be performed in these spaces, unless they are more specialized.

Table 4. Chart showing by country the CNC used in their spaces. Source: Own elaboration.

3.7 Differences by countries

France follows the guidelines and ratios discussed at the European level in terms of software.

Located in second or third place with respect to the presence of lasers in spaces, not so with medium or large CNC milling systems that are the country that is below the average in last place (43% below the European average, with 67.2%). Together with Spain, it is the country with the presence of all spaces with 3D printers, as well as the opposite with thermoforming systems, which occupies the last place with 14% of spaces that have this type of equipment. It is also significant that it is the second country with the fewest VR or AR devices in its spaces after Germany, although it is the second with the most devices per space (43%). Regarding the equipment that complements the space, it is above the European average, especially in resources oriented towards electronics.

Greece, according to the sampling carried out, maintains similar patterns in terms of software, except in the case of programming, compared to the European average. It should be noted in general terms, that it is the country that shows the most deficit in terms of resources in its spaces, not having CNC

metal cutters or any type of metrology devices. It is true that these are not the equipment that prevail in Europe as a whole, but the results regarding 3D printing (in which 77% do not have any equipment), sewing or embroidery machines (only 17% with this type of equipment), and even electronic devices (67% lack resources), are below average. Yes, a greater number of VR or AR equipment is noticed that are close to the European average, or that half of the spaces sampled, have one or two lasers. In a similar way it happens with the presence of milling machines, both medium-large and small. Even lacking machinery, the Greek spaces have basic electronic equipment in most of their facilities.

In Germany, the scenario shows that the spaces are prepared at the level of software, especially design, although they remain at averages comparable to the European average, except for presentations, which is well established in German spaces (83.3%). Regarding the machinery, it is very remarkable that all of them are equipped with lasers, being the only country that completes this data in the sampling, and it is considerable that half of them have two lasers. This presence is also shared in the volume of milling machines of medium or large dimension, since all are equipped with these means, also being the only country in Europe with this data. Regarding 3D printing resources, it is noteworthy that all the spaces sampled have more than two printers in their facilities (83%, above the European ratio of 68.3). Half of the spaces have thermoforming machines, even 17% have two teams. Together with Greece, it is the country with the least implementation of 3D scanning systems. 67% of the spaces have more than two sewing or embroidery machines, and they are the most prepared country in terms of VR/AR resources in all of Europe, since 83% of their facilities are equipped with these systems (including the 50% of them have more than two devices). They have the best reference in that all their facilities are equipped with material and mechanical tools to satisfy any job.

Denmark, along with France and Spain, have the best data in terms of software implementation, exceeding the European ratio in all cases, especially in 2D-3D design. There is a significant percentage in the use of data software in the whole of the European average, with 85.7% (at the same levels as manufacturing software). Of the average configuration of equipment, it is the country with the most deficit in cutting-engraving lasers (only 43% of the spaces have it), compared to other cases such as Germany and Spain, and in terms of the use of small milling machines (at the tail of this type of equipment, with an implantation that does not exceed 43%). On the other hand, the numbers improve in terms of medium-large milling machines (still behind Germany and Spain, with 71%), and in the case of 3D printing, which are the second country in the integration of these systems, especially using more than two in the resources they have in 72% of the facilities. It is striking that they are the country with the highest implementation of sewing or embroidery machines in Europe (86% of a European average of 52.5%). On the other hand, in terms of electronic devices and virtual reality equipment, they have enough technological deficit, that this last case, reaches only 14% implementation. By contrast, together with Spain, they have the best equipped facilities, in terms of mechanical, electronic, or painting resources.

Italy is more predisposed to programming software (71.4%) together with Spain. Also with Spain, it is the second country with one laser per space (57%) and together with France, after Germany, with two lasers in 29% of Italian spaces. However, together with Greece, there are still 43% of spaces without a medium or large milling machine and 29% without 3D printers, while 14% spaces have a CNC metal cutting system (which also reaches that figure with spaces that have more than two such systems). It is the second country, behind Spain in the largest number of small milling machines and next to France, of those with the fewest vinyl cutters. 28% have more than two plotter printing systems, and a significant number of spaces have one (43%) or more 3D scanners (28%). Together with Denmark, they have several spaces that are above the average with respect to having a sewing or embroidery machine (57%). They have more than two electronic devices in each space (29%) and more than two also in the case of virtual or augmented reality equipment (57% of the sample).

Finally, Spain, it must be said that it has 2D-3D design and manufacturing software in all its spaces (above the rest of the countries) and reaches a very high number of makerspaces that handle programming software (with 90, 9%, also above the rest). It also once again has the best percentage in software for making presentations (well above the rest, with 63.6%). The number of lasers in the country is considerable, since 73% have at least one laser in each space and only 9% of the sample do

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not (only Germany exceeds these figures for all countries with at least one laser in each space). Almost the same situation is repeated as with the milling machines (70% of the spaces have one, with 88 milling machines in the country of medium or large size), only surpassed in number by Germany. The number of spaces with more than two 3D printers is also relevant data, which indicates a commitment to this type of technology. However, as in Greece, there is a lack of any CNC metal cutting system. Regarding the number of small milling machines, the percentage is the highest in Europe (73% of spaces with at least one), and in terms of a thermoforming system, 46% indicate having one (which means 54 systems of this type in the spaces sampled, average surpassed by Denmark). It is worth highlighting the number of 3D scanning devices compared to Europe (112 are counted in eleven spaces, which represent 82% of the country), electronic devices (only 9% would not have), and the number of reality equipment virtual or augmented (37% still would not have this type of equipment) is only surpassed by Germany. Lastly, the spaces do not show interest in metrology equipment, as only 9% of the spaces would have some type of system of these characteristics.

4 Conclusions

The collaborative way of working in the spaces encourages and validates that these meetings between makers, manufacturers and users can take place, either because they already work with companies and it is clear that they are the main client, and they work with users, even in a more specific sense, that intervenes doing or building their things with a certain ability that they have learned or acquire in these spaces.

From the sampling and the results obtained, we have obtained answers from the productive and social philosophy that surround the FabLab or European makerspace models, and with this information it can allow us to see which the appropriate model is to introduce users and companies in that chain. or cycle of value necessary for its best operation.

We have seen that some spaces lack sufficient resources like those of the industry, but they are used to doing work for the company and these, in turn, do not have 'laboratory' resources to prototype and validate their products as spaces have. sampled. Its position, around the possibilities of making prototypes, can be expanded by providing companies with a collaborative model with makers and co-designing with potential users.

Apart from prototyping or laboratory technologies, we have come to observe that answers can not only be obtained from physical prototypes during the development and construction of the user's ideas, but also the use of technologies such as virtual or augmented reality are beginning to see implemented in these spaces.

Table 4. The strengths and weaknesses, based on the table from FabLab Global Survey (University of Santander), the authors have expanded and completed its definition (completed in grey underline and expanded in the second additional tables in each section). Source: Authors' own, based on LENA-ACEBO and GARCÍA-RUIZ, 2016.

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Allow access to Open culture. ▪ To bring technology to <u>the young.</u> ▪ To generate a community around technology. ▪ <u>Facilitate accessibility to create and fabricate digitally.</u> ▪ Collaborate with multiple groups and associations. ▪ To be part of <u>different networks, especially international ones.</u> ▪ Development of several joint programmes with other entities. ▪ <u>Bringing the Maker world closer to its area of influence.</u> ▪ To have a suitable space for creation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Obtain the necessary financing. ▪ Improve or expand the machinery. ▪ Build a suitable ecosystem. ▪ Obtain more space in the facilities. ▪ Economic sustainability. ▪ <u>Proper project documentation</u> ▪ Maintain an Open culture. ▪ Attracting more users and increasing participation. ▪ Generate a suitable business model.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Significant presence on social networks. ▪ Access to 2D and 3D software. ▪ Appearance in the media on a regular basis. ▪ Teams made up of graduates in technological training. ▪ Decision-making does not hinder their activity. ▪ Prototyping services work. ▪ They have their own financial resources. ▪ Work with companies and professional profiles. ▪ Designers are the main teeth. ▪ Business models with people of mature age. ▪ Very active organizations. ▪ They have quite specialized users. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of people dedicated to communication. ▪ Little metal cutting technology. ▪ No strategic investment. ▪ Failure to specialise or look for new training niches. ▪ Dependence in many aspects on public funding. ▪ It is necessary to consider that the spaces are not sufficiently prepared. ▪ Compatibility between online and face-to-face. ▪ Not having digitised processes. ▪ Not having tools that facilitate Innovation (non-technological).

Table 5. The threats and opportunities, based on the table from FabLab Global Survey (University of Santander), the authors have expanded and completed its definition (completed in grey underline and expanded in the second additional tables in each section). Source: Authors' own, based on Lena-Acebo and García-Ruiz, 2016.

THREATS	OPPORTUNITIES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No sustainable business model. ▪ Geographical location or <u>poor access.</u> ▪ Lack of innovative culture. ▪ Difficulties of financing and sustainability. ▪ Absence of a suitable space. ▪ No new ideas. ▪ Lack of understanding of the FabLab or Makerspace concept. ▪ Loss of support from institutions. ▪ The supply parts and specific products. ▪ Lack of connection with other <u>spaces.</u> ▪ Lack of infrastructure for other projects. ▪ Lack of timely staff. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Location close to universities. ▪ Establish collaboration with multiple entities. ▪ Collaborate with other entities to expand the <u>Maker culture.</u> ▪ Location in a business incubator. ▪ High capacity of the project teams. ▪ Great new ideas (<u>source of innovations.</u>). ▪ Great versatility (<u>due to multidisciplinary work.</u>). ▪ <u>To be the first space in its area of influence.</u> ▪ <u>To take advantage of the visibility of the Maker movement (because of Covid).</u> ▪ <u>To be part of an institution with an important.</u> ▪ Number of users.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dependence on investments in salaries, rent, maintenance and purchase of new machines. ▪ Dependence on publicly funded projects. ▪ Dependence on the same training programme. ▪ Failure to make the most of the future relationship that currently exists with students. ▪ Organisational difficulties to serve the user well. ▪ Very young business models. ▪ Not being specialised (in a subject or sector). ▪ Closing themselves off to other future possibilities. ▪ Not adapting their facilities as much as possible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3D printing as a step towards additive manufacturing (Industry 4.0). ▪ Small, well-equipped production centres. ▪ Progressive availability of VR equipment. ▪ Prepared with electronic devices. ▪ Trained teams that boost creativity. ▪ Being small units allows them to be more flexible. ▪ Contribute their know-how in R&D services. ▪ Being in contact with institutions. ▪ Face-to-face activities with different disciplines are increasingly present. ▪ Innovative model despite the time of existence. ▪ The spaces have different types of business models. ▪ Continue to take advantage of and strengthen their relationship in networks.

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Annex

Questionnaire proposed for this study.

According to the responding countries: 11 Spain, 7 Italy, 7 Denmark, 6 Germany, 6 Greece and 7 France.
In total: 44 spaces.

Dear participant, welcome to our survey/questionnaire!

The survey lasts about 5-10 minutes. There are no right or wrong answers, this is about your views.

All data is anonymized, and your privacy is guaranteed.

Thank you for helping us gather relevant information!

With this survey we aim at collecting information regarding people's, makers' and manufacturers' perceptions, opinions and needs regarding the maker movement, collaborative manufacturing and co-creation schemes between individual makers, consumers, and manufacturing enterprises.

***Obligatory**

1. ORGANISATION ACTIVITY

1.1. Which of these definitions describes better your organization?

- Professional or business association/ federation.
- User community or informal group (e.g. P2P initiatives).
- Cooperative or social enterprise.
- Non-governmental organization (NGO).
- University research group or center.
- Public institution.
- Technology Centre.
- Small-Medium Enterprises.
- Large Company.
- Start-up.
- Vocational training.
- Non-higher education centre.

1.2. Participation in organization's networks.

- National network project.
- Local or regional network project.
- International network project.
-

1.3. Themes of the networks in which you participate.

- Design.
- Hardware/electronics.
- 3D printing.
- Do-It-Yourself (DIY).
- Other digital manufacturing resources (not 3D printing).
- Trading platforms (products).
- Collaborative networks (creation and production).

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- Institutional networks.
- Business networks.
- Others.

1.4. Year your organization was founded.

1.5. Current status of the organization.

- Active: commercially active.
- No commercial activity.
- Pending.

2. VALUES AND STRATEGIES.

2.1. The organization supports the following values:

- Technological empowerment.
- Technology Observatory.
- Self-learning and digital education.
- Open data.
- Hacktivism.
- Open Hardware / Design.
- Open Software.

2.2. The organization shares other values not mentioned above:

- Urban Innovation.
- Digital Inclusion.
- Circular Economy.
- Creative Commons.
- Activist Design.
- Other, please specify.

2.3. Which actions transmit the indicated values through?

- Media.
- Open access cultural content.
- Management of the physical space.
- Service Provider.
- Management of community networks.
- Organization of workshops and courses.
- Organization of specific events.
- Development of research projects.
- Manufacturing with open hardware.
- Development with open software.
- Free technology support.
- Development of social innovation projects.
- Others (please specify).

2.4. How does the organization carry out its activities?

- Online only (virtually).
- Offline only (physically).
- Online and offline.

2.5. What kind of place do you use to do it offline?

- Private open.
- Private Restricted.
- Public.
- Leased.

2.6. Are the facilities adapted for your purposes?

- Yes, totally.
- Partially or in process.
- At a starting point.
- Not adapted.

2.7. Where are the areas for the activities you carried out?

- Neighbourhood-District.
- Within your town/City.
- Regional/provincial.
- State/Country.
- European.
- International/ Global.

2.8. Type of product usually developed.

- Fixing things (Bricolage).
- Build prototypes (professional).
- Working on models and mock-ups (hobby).
- Personal initiative.
- Others.

2.9. Users' profiles.

- Student.
- Inventor.
- Designer.
- Architect.
- Electronic Engineer or technician.
- Informatic Engineer or technician.
- Mechatronic Engineer or technician.
- Mechanical Engineers or technician.
- Technology Teacher.
- Researcher.
- Artist.

2.10. Project profile.

- Mechanical accuracy.
- Product design.
- Architecture.
- Merchandising or communication.
- Software development or programming.
- Robotics projects.
- Electronics projects.
- Training projects for children and young people.
- Adult education projects.
- Other.

3. PARTNERSHIPS AND FUNDING.

3.1. What type of entities does the organization collaborate with?

- Public (non-educational) institutions.
- Private companies (non-educational).
- Professional and business associations.
- Neighbourhood Associations.
- NGOs.
- Educational Centres.
- Non-formal groups.
- Individuals.

3.2. What kind of entities does your organization receive grants, financial assistance, money from?

- Private for profit: Venture capital, Private equity, Business angels, ...
- Private Non-Profit.
- Public institutions: Universities, Public corporations...
- Self-financing.
- No income (Venture capital, Private equity, Business angels, Foundations, etc).

3.3. Main activities for the financing of your organization.

- Direct public funding.
- Private sponsorships.
- Associated fees.
- Grants by competitive call.
- Parties and recreational events.
- Crowdfunding.
- Training activities.
- Donations.
- Financial support from the organization you belong to.
- Advertising.
- Specialized events (not training).
- Own merchandising.
- Informal contributions from people in the organization (not quotas).
- Rent of spaces.
- Machine rental.

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- Punctual rental of space.
- Prototyping services.
- R&D Services.

3.4. What the money is usually invested in?

- Maintenance of space and technology.
- To pay for the activities: transport, accommodation, materials, etc.
- Investment in advertising and dissemination.
- Payroll payments, fees to collaborators.
- Acquisition of machinery or technology.
- Materials and Consumables Complaint.
- Volunteer expenses.
- Training.

4. INTERNAL INFRASTRUCTURE

4.1. How many people are involved in the organization on a regular basis?

4.2. How many people are involved within the organization to make a decision?

4.3. If you could set an average, what would you say about them?

- Level of education.
- Gender.
- Age range.

4.4. How many are employed? If you could set an average, what would you say about them?

- Level of education.
- Gender.
- Age range.

4.5. Technology skills. If you could set an average, what would you say about them?

- Yes.
- No.
- Partially.

4.6. Soft skills training.

- Creativity.
- Teamwork.
- Management and organization.
- Communication.
- Documentation.
- Others, please specify.

4.7. Other training aspects.

- Economy and administration.
- Innovation.

- Quality.
- Environment.
- Marketing.
- Safety and Occupational Risks.
- Marketing.
- IPR.

4.8. Do you make users complete any training to become part of the organization?

- Basic enabling training is required.
- We provide introductory training.
- We carry out continuous training.
- We carry out informal training for accompaniment.
- No training required.

5. COMMUNICATION AND TOOLS.

5.1. We have people dedicated to communication.

- Yes, professional subcontractors.
- Yes, professional associates.
- Yes, associates but not professionals.
- No.

5.2. Does your organization have resources to communicate and disseminate its activities?

- Yes.
 - Personal.
 - digital tools.
 - Budget.
- No.

5.3. Does your organization regularly report the developed projects?

- Daily.
- Weekly.
- Monthly.
- Quarterly.
- Half-yearly.
- Yearly.
- Never.

5.4. Whom does your organization regularly report the developed projects?

5.5 Has your organization been in the media?

- Interviews.
- Debates or discussions.
- Current news.
- Press release Advertisement.
- Others.

5.6. Do you update your website?

- Daily.
- Weekly.
- Monthly.
- Quarterly.
- Half-yearly.
- Yearly.
- Never.
-

5.7. (Types of) Communication tools (internal and external).

- Regular mobile phone contact.
- Social networking.
- Email address.
- Contact for events.
- Internal organization.
- File sharing and storage.
- Web management.
- Video blogging.
- Streaming stuff.

6. TECHNOLOGY.

6.1. Software (free or commercial).

- 3D-2D Design.
- Programming.
- Manufacturing.
- Data.
- Administration.
- Presentations.
- Other (please indicate).

6.2. Digital devices (number and technology).

- Laser (<90, 90/100, >100).
- Medium large milling machine (3, 4, 5 axes or robot).
- 3D printing (FFF, SLS, SLA or other).
- Metal cutting machine (oxyfuel, plasma, laser).
- Small milling machine.
- Vinyl Plotter.
- Print plotter (b/w, color).
- 3D Scanner.
- Sewing or embroidery machines.
- PCB and other electronics production machines.
- Metrology equipment (CMM, tomography, etc.).
- AV/VR equipment's (Glasses and Virtual or Augmented Reality).

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6.3. Other important devices (mechanical, electronic).

Machinery.

Tool.

THANK YOU

Thank you for taking part in this survey and contributing to our understanding of what people think about makerspaces and collaborative manufacturing between individual makers and manufacturer enterprises.

Your input will help us a great deal to identify key elements and perceptions that should be considered during the implementation of our project.